

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Sales of Djakarta Transport Jaya

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ABSTRACT: PT Djakarta Transport Jaya faced profit problems five years ago, one of which was the lack of knowledge about the right marketing strategy and limited access to a wide marketing platform. The author conducts quantitative research through surveys and in-depth interviews with new potential market segments that can help PT Djakarta Transport Jaya increase sales in the B2B market. The author also analyzes the factors that can influence the buying interest of new market candidates of PT Djakarta Transport Jaya. The results of this research are expected to be a solution for PT Djakarta Transport Jaya in increasing profits through the implementation of appropriate marketing strategies and optimization of access to extensive marketing platforms. Thus, PT Djakarta Transport Jaya can reach new potential markets and increase its competitiveness in the B2B market. The analysis was conducted internally using: Segmenting, targeting and positioning, Marketing mix, VRIO Framework and Business Model Canvas, as well as external analysis consisting of Porter 5 forces, PESTEL analysis, Competitor analysis and Consumer analysis. The results of the author's research, PT Djakarta Transport Jaya can emphasize a wide reach to remote areas by upholding the speed and security of shipments on social media platforms. Using social media marketing such as the use of IG ADS, FB ADS and TikTok to reach new consumers by highlighting the completeness of the fleet. Focus on a sophisticated tracking system and service activities carried out by SDM Djakarta transport jaya. Strengthening social media content with interesting topics such as technological innovations such as IoT which is used to monitor the performance and punctuality of vehicle trips to increase customer satisfaction and lastly Keeping prices competitive with competitors in order to attract new customers and retain old customers.

KEYWORDS: PT Djakarta Transport Jaya, marketing strategy, sales increase

INTRODUCTION

The shipping expedition industry in Indonesia is highly competitive, and companies must focus on increasing their credibility to attract consumers. This industry is a mainstay for Indonesia and was a major contributor to the country's 5.44% economic growth in the second quarter of 2022, with transportation and warehousing leading the way with 21.27% growth. Other sectors that contributed to the growth included accommodation and food and drink, electricity and gas procurement, other services, information and communication, and corporate services.

PT Djakarta Transport Jaya is a transportation company that has been established for 27 years, providing fast and safe shipping services. However, the company is facing a challenge in increasing its target market and sales. Through further research, the main problem was identified as a lack of brand awareness due to a name change in 2018. The company has loyal customers who appreciate the quality service, responsibility for delivery security, and competitive prices with competitors. However, the company has failed to build brand awareness for new customers, resulting in stagnant sales and overreliance on existing customers.

To address this problem, the author proposes conducting further research to determine effective marketing strategies that can increase brand awareness, attract new customers, and increase sales. The research questions include identifying the factors that influence PT Djakarta Transport Jaya's brand awareness and proposing appropriate improvements to existing marketing strategies. The results of this research can provide valuable insights for the company to optimize its marketing efforts and distinguish its transportation services from other competitors in the market. Effective and creative marketing strategies, such as online marketing and identifying the right target audience, can help the company to increase consumer interest and create a competitive advantage for the company. By implementing these strategies, PT Djakarta Transport Jaya can attract more customers and ultimately increase its profits and success in the transportation industry.

METHODOLOGY

This article discusses a research project that focuses on the business operations of PT Djakarta Transport Jaya. The study employs

quantitative research methods to identify and understand the issues affecting the company. The research process consists of six stages, starting with problem identification and finishing with the reporting and evaluation of results. Questionnaires and other media sources, such as reports, books, journals, articles, and websites, were used to collect data. Qualitative data was collected from individuals using open-ended questions, and a total of two participants were interviewed in May 2023. The data collected from questionnaires and other sources were analyzed using both external and internal analysis methods. External analysis involved the use of the PESTEL Framework, Five Forces Model, Customer Analysis, and Competitor Analysis, while internal analysis employed the Resource-Based View Model, STP Model, Marketing Mix 7P, and VRIO analysis. A SWOT analysis was conducted to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of PT Djakarta Transport Jaya, and a Root Cause Analysis was carried out to determine the source of the company's revenue decline. Finally, a QSPM strategy matrix was used to formulate and propose a strategy and its implementation plan to PT Djakarta Transport Jaya.

LITERATURE REVIEW PESTEL FRAMEWORK

PESTEL Analysis is an analytical method used to identify the external factors that affect an organization, namely Political, Economic, Social, Technology, Legal, and Environment. It provides a complete picture of the environment in which a company operates and enables the company to predict future situations and conditions. PESTEL analysis is a valuable tool in strategy management and can help companies make informed decisions. This framework was introduced by Fathi Salem M. A and is commonly used in business and finance.

CONSUMER ANALYSIS

Consumer analysis is the process of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data related to consumer behavior, preferences, and needs in order to develop effective marketing strategies. The goal is to understand consumer motivations and preferences in purchasing decision making and obtain greater opportunities to develop products or services that suit their needs. Consumer analysis can be done through various methods, such as literature review, surveys, interviews, observation, and data analysis. This becomes important for companies in developing the right marketing strategy and can increase their competitiveness in the market. Collect information about why people buy or don't buy our products and services (East Bay SBDC Article). All of this external information is a source of internal judgment to improve our business.

FIVE FORCES MODEL

Michael E. Porter developed the Five Forces analysis model, which includes the threat of newcomers, bargaining power of buyers, threat of substitute products or services, bargaining power of suppliers, and competition among existing competitors. This model is used to analyze the external environment of an industry, and to formulate competitive strategies. The Five Forces analysis allows companies to view the competitive dynamics of their industry, and to make strategic decisions accordingly. These factors can be applied to social, environmental, and business activities, and help companies understand their position within the market.

COMPETITOR ANALYSIS

Competition is one of the unavoidable factors in business today. Regardless of the size of the company, there are competitors in the industry whose strategy influences the strategic planning process. Competitive analysis guides organizational strategy and influences how companies in their industry behave or react. Companies conduct competitive analysis to measure and/or evaluate their position relative to their competitors. The company must not ignore its competitors and must understand who our competitors are. (Philip Kotler, 2003). Understanding and knowing our competitors greatly helps our company to offer better products and services.

SEGMENTATION, TARGETING, AND POSITIONING MODEL

The Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning (STP) marketing model is used by companies to develop the right message and marketing strategy for their product or service. It involves dividing the market into specific segments, determining the targeted segments, and developing a unique position in the market. This model can help improve marketing effectiveness and differentiate products from competitors. Segmentation envisions more prospects, targeting chooses profitable segments, and positioning forms the brand image perceived by consumers. (Philip Kotler, 2003).

MARKETING MIX 7P

Marketing mix analysis is a combination of a company's tactical marketing instruments used to evoke the desired response from the target market. It consists of four P's: product, price, place, and promotion. Some add three more elements: people, process, and physical evidence. Companies use this concept to ensure their marketing messages reach the right consumers, at the right time, and

in the right way, to maximize the effectiveness of their marketing strategies. (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

VRIO

The VRIO framework is a tool used to measure internal analysis by asking four questions about a company's resources or capabilities to determine their competitive potential. The four questions are: value, rarity, inimitability, and organization. The elements include valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and organized. If a company successfully identifies all four components of the VRIO framework, it achieves sustainable competitive advantage. (Pearson/Prentice Hall, Aribowo, 2021, Cardeal, 2012, Newbert, 2008, Durand, 2010).

SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT analysis is a methodology used to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the external environment of a company, organization, or situation. By utilizing this approach, strategies can be developed to maximize strengths and opportunities, while minimizing the impact of threats and weaknesses. (Seki & Biler, 2016 cited in Ermetin, 2023).

RESULT

ANALYSIS OF EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL ENVIRONMENTS

This chapter will discuss the analysis and business strategies that will be adopted in this study. The author will discuss the analysis of the internal and external situation of the company PT Djakarta Transport Jaya with the aim of finding solutions to business problems that are being faced today. The results of the research will produce strategic suggestions that will help the company in overcoming these problems.

External analysis

Porter 5 Strengths

A study on the truck transportation industry utilized Porter's Five Forces analysis to determine industry competitiveness, including the threat of new entrants, competition among firms, substitution threats, consumer bargaining power, and supplier bargaining power. This analysis can help companies develop effective business strategies to compete in the market:

A. New Arrivals Threat:

Djakarta transport jaya services include the transportation industry that focuses on transporting goods in large quantities so that vehicles are needed including truck groups which certainly require a lot of capital if someone wants to build a business like Djakarta transport jaya. This means that it will be difficult for new businesses to enter the market because it requires a lot of capital to buy vehicles that are able to load goods in large quantities. So based on this, the threat of newcomers is categorized as **low**.

B. Threat of Substitution:

PT Djakarta Transport Jaya can experience the threat of alternative products such as industrial logistics services (Samudera logistic) which are increasing and continue to innovate along with technological advances, but their prices are quite high if they want to transport goods in large quantities. Therefore, companies need to consider companies that want to use services from samudera logistics at prices that are quite much more expensive than Djakarta transportation jaya. So based on this, it is categorized as **low**.

C. Bargaining Power of Suppliers:

PT Djakarta Transport Jaya relies on suppliers of fuel, spare parts, and infrastructure to run its operations. Therefore, companies should consider the reliability, availability, and supplier alternatives to reduce the risk of depending on a single supplier. With abundant fuel, Djakarta transport triumphant to find other suppliers. So based on this, it is categorized as **Low**.

D. Buyer's Bargaining Power:

In the transportation industry, for Djakarta transport Jaya customers include B2B with the average from companies that have long been consumers of Djakarta Transport Jaya. This is because they have believed in the services provided by Djakarta transport Jaya so far. and until now they still use the services of Djakarta transport Jaya. Therefore, it can be said that consumers from Djakarta transport Jaya do not easily move to competitors of Djakarta transport Jaya. So based on this, it is categorized as **low**.

D. Competition In The Industry:

The transportation industry is generally quite competitive, and PT Djakarta Transport Jaya is no exception. However, the completeness of the fleet owned by Djakarta Transport Jaya makes it quite difficult for consumers to find other cargo services considering that Djakarta transportation Jaya includes a cargo transportation company that is quite flexible with its fleet and prices that are negotiable to old and new players. So based on this, it is categorized as **low**.

PESTEL Analysis

The PESTEL framework covers political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that may have an impact on business. Analysis:

A. Politics (Opportunity)

Indonesia is entering the period leading to the 2024 General Elections which political conditions tend to be stable, despite several controversial issues being debated. The government will continue implementing large-scale policies such as national economic recovery and infrastructure improvement. PT Djakarta Transport Jaya has an opportunity to benefit from strong political support and policies supporting the transportation sector, including investment in transportation infrastructure and improved public transportation services.

B. Economy (opportunity)

Indonesia's projected economic growth of 4.9-5.2% in 2023 is still positive and can lead to increased government funding for transportation infrastructure, creating opportunities for logistics companies. Monitoring economic factors is important for logistics companies to make informed decisions and mitigate risks. The government's national economic recovery programs and policies also support the transportation sector and present opportunities for companies like PT Djakarta Transport Jaya to develop competitive business strategies in response to economic changes.

C. Social (Opportunity)

Since the PPKM rule has been lifted, increased travel has resulted in high levels of traffic congestion and pressure on transportation companies to provide fast and accurate services. Transportation industry players can consider these social factors when designing effective and responsive business strategies to meet changing social conditions in Indonesia.

D. Technology (opportunity)

Technological factors, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), can significantly affect transportation companies. IoT can provide benefits to transportation companies such as real-time monitoring of fuel consumption, vehicle conditions, and performance. IoT can also optimize operational efficiency, reduce operational costs, increase customer satisfaction, and improve road safety. Examples of IoT implementation in transportation include traffic management systems and road condition monitoring to prevent congestion.

E. Environment (Opportunity)

The environmental condition of Djakarta Jaya transportation in Jakarta which is now hot has not become a temporary opportunity to expedite the company's operations because there is no flooding in the process of shipping goods to various regions. DKI Jakarta and surrounding areas are vulnerable to flooding during the rainy season. In addition, Jakarta's congested condition is a challenge for Djakarta Transports Jaya to deliver its goods quickly and safely to customers.

F. Law (Opportunity).

The transportation industry in Indonesia faces challenges related to strict environmental and transportation safety regulations, as well as a complicated bureaucracy for licensing and vehicle approval. PP No. 13 of 2017 National Spatial Plan provides zoning regulation directives for the National Transportation Network System with the aim of regulating the optimal use of space and minimizing the negative environmental impact of transportation. These legal conditions pose challenges for the transportation industry in Indonesia.

Competitor analysis

PT Djakarta Transport Jaya seems to have an edge in terms of services when compared to its two competitors. Their services include direct fleet GPS tracking for consumers and faster delivery times, which are not provided by their competitors. Additionally, PT Djakarta Transport Jaya has a more complete fleet compared to their competitors.

Consumer analytics

Through in-depth interviews with some potential customers, it was found that social media is very important in building brand awareness of a product or service and increasing consumer buying interest. Brand awareness is also crucial in promoting and increasing consumer buying interest in a brand or product. Consumers consider service, price, and product availability when deciding whether to use a service or buy a product. The quality of service and affordable prices can influence consumer perceptions of a service or product.

Internal analysis

STP

When starting a business, the STP model helps marketers prioritize offers, create and deliver personalized and relevant messages, and engage different audiences, thus helping to create a marketing plan. STP Kudimon Healthy Food is provided with the following analysis:

Segmentation

Based on the segmentation analysis, it can be seen that PT Djakarta Transport Jaya has three segmentations with three types of industries and products/goods delivered each differently.

Targeting

As a company engaged in cargo transportation with company to company (B2B), the target of PT Djakarta Transport Jaya is regular customers, loyal customers, potential customers namely stevedoring companies, construction project companies, iron companies and sugar companies.

Position

Position statement	Description: _____
Target Segment	Companies engaged in the distribution sector of goods, manufacturing companies, retail, and so on that want to ship goods in large quantities with on-time delivery services and delivery at affordable costs.
Consumer Issues	Companies often find it difficult to get a safe fleet in protecting goods in the process of shipping goods. Many small companies often ship goods but do not have their own fleet Companies need third-party logistics services to reduce their operational costs, as they avoid investing in physical infrastructure, vehicles, and personnel.
Consumer job to be done	Companies need a fleet to deliver their goods in order to deliver goods more efficiently, quickly, safely and reliably.
Terms of Reference	Logistics companies that specialize in delivering heavy goods such as iron, and construction. Logistics companies that provide delivery of goods are not only urban areas but can be to inland or remote areas.
Basic Requirements	Has a transportation service car in the form of Colt diesel, Trenton, and trailer.
Unique Value Proposition	All fleets are equipped with GPS for consumers to monitor the fleet during the delivery process.
Reason to believe	A logistics company that has 3 complete car vehicles to offer to companies with fast, safe and affordable freight forwarding services that are still used by customers since the 1997s.
distinguished from competitors	Has an extensive network and has extensive services to areas outside JABODETABEK such as West Java. Unlike its competitors only in the JABODETABEK and Banten areas.

Marketing mix (current)

1. The results are land transportation: iron transportation services, construction and sea freight forwarders: export and import transportation services at ports
2. Price with price strategy: receivables, using DP first if it has been paid off until the shipment has just been paid off and the price is in accordance with the distance of delivery. Then for the price of a colt diesel car: IDR 1,000,000-IDR 5,000,000 (ordinary shipping changes depending on the distance), tronton size cars: IDR 1,500,000-IDR 6,000,000 (ordinary shipping changes depending on distance) and 40 feet trailer size cars: IDR 2,000,000-IDR 7,000,000 (ordinary shipping changes depending on distance). So the price is based on cost based because the determination of the selling price of the product is based on the costs incurred, such as operational and non-operational costs
3. Place: Jalan Peternakan No 19, Kapuk Jakarta Barat and Jalan Peternakan No 18, Kapuk Jakarta Barat. Strategic place: close to iron storage warehouses and close to Tanjung Priuk Port.

4. Promotions: advertising through social media: wa and djakartatransport.com websites, visits to companies, call center marketing
5. People: staff, management and customer service.
6. Process: make a fleet reservation, the fleet arrives at the loading location, the process of loading goods into the fleet, the fleet goes to the unloading location, the process of unloading goods. The fleet is ready to carry new goods.
7. Physical evidence: website, fleet, signage, customer review, office, employee and fleet pool

VRIO

PT Djakarta Transport Jaya conducted a VRIO analysis to determine their resources that provide sustainable competitive advantage including manufacturing location, distribution channels, advanced load tracking systems, skilled human resources, experienced management, and extensive partnership connections. Conducting the analysis effectively can help companies maximize the utilization of their resources for better business performance and market competitiveness.

Internal Analysis

SWOT and TOWS matrix

After identifying the SWOT, the TOWS matrix for the business solution is:

Table 5. SWOT and TOWS Matrix

	<p>Strength Fleet completeness Competitive price Have a good reputation with customers. Has a sophisticated tracking system Skilled HR Manufacturing location & Distribution channels to reach consumers more easily Wide delivery coverage to remote areas. Fast and secure delivery</p>	<p>Weakness 1.Brand awareness is still lacking after company name change 2. Advertising through social media is still lacking. 3. Do not have a fleet of environmentally friendly vehicles. 4. Social media content has not attracted from the low quality of each image. 5. Social media posts are still rare.</p>
	Strategy SO	Strategy WO
<p>Chance Improvement of transportation infrastructure from the government. The difficulty of new competitors in this industry. Technological advances in the form of IoT in the company's operational efficiency. Quality service can increase customer interest. Competitive prices can increase customer interest Social media marketing can increase brand awareness</p>	<p>Using social media marketing such as the use of IG ADS, FB ADS and TikTok to reach new consumers by highlighting the completeness of the fleet. (S1, S7, O2, O6.) Keep prices competitive with competitors in order to attract new customers and retain old customers. (S2, S3, S6, O1, O5). Emphasize wide reach to remote areas by upholding the speed and security of delivery on social media platforms. (S7, S8, O1, O2, O6) Focus on a sophisticated tracking system and service activities carried out by SDM Djakarta transport Jaya. (S3, S4, S5, S8, O3, O4, O5, O6)</p>	<p>Increase advertising on various social media with a focus on emphasizing that the company has changed its new name and continues to maintain good relationships with customers. (WO1, WO2, W4, W5, OO4, O5, O6) Strengthening social media content with interesting topics such as technological innovations such as IoT which is used to monitor the performance and punctuality of vehicle trips to increase customer satisfaction. (WO 2, WO4, WO5, O3,O4,O6) Companies can make changes in travel operational systems such as routes traveled and operating hours to optimize vehicle usage. As well as operational cost savings (WO3, O1, O4,O5)</p>
	Strategy ST	Strategy WT
challenge	The process of shipping goods with the use of IoT is also to monitor and manage vehicle routes,	The allocation of funds is prioritized on rebranding through social media by

<p>Jakarta's congested environmental conditions. DKI Jakarta and surrounding areas are vulnerable to flooding during the rainy season which can affect transportation routes in the JABODETABEK area. Strict regulations related to the environment and transportation safety. Wages in Jakarta are among the highest minimum wages in Indonesia</p>	<p>optimize the delivery of goods, and improve safety on the road. (S3, S4, S8, T1, T2, T3) Companies need to cooperate with the government and comply with regulations related to the environment and transportation safety to ensure they can operate legally and according to applicable regulations. (S3, S4, S6, T3). Make cost savings by optimizing production and operational processes by identifying unnecessary activities, or considering more effective use of technology. (S5, S6,S8, T1, T2,T4)</p>	<p>using technology to improve customer service and generate interest. (W1,W2,W3,W4,W5, T1) Promoting the efforts of the DKI Jakarta government in overcoming congestion Together with fast and safe services from Djakarta Transport Jaya (W1,W2,W3,W4,W5, T1, T2, T3)</p>
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Source: Author Analysis

Table VI.12 Strategy Alternatives Ranking

	Strategy Description	Rank	QSPM Score
SO3	Emphasize wide reach to remote areas by upholding the speed and security of delivery on social media platforms	1	7,08
SO1	Using social media marketing such as the use of IG ADS, FB ADS and TikTok to reach new consumers by highlighting the completeness of the fleet	2	6,85
SO3	Focus on a sophisticated tracking system and service activities carried out by SDM Djakarta transport Jaya.	3	6,81
WO2	Strengthening social media content with interesting topics such as technological innovations such as IoT which is used to monitor the performance and punctuality of vehicle trips to increase customer satisfaction	4	6,65
SO4	Keeping prices competitive with competitors in order to attract new customers and retain existing customers	5	6,14

Source: QSPM Result

After conducting a QSPM analysis, it is determined by identifying alternative strategies that obtain the highest score and ranking. A higher score signifies the preferred option for implementation. Conversely, a low score indicates that a particular approach is unfair and unworthy of adoption by the company.

Business solutions

- The QSPM analysis produced four strategies for Djakarta Transport Jaya to attract new customers and increase sales. Strategies include emphasizing delivery speed & security on social media, using social media marketing to highlight fleet completeness, focus on sophisticated tracking system & service quality, strengthening social media content with IoT technology, and keeping prices competitive. These strategies require continuous monitoring and improvement to meet market trends and customer needs.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research, there are several factors that can influence the purchase intention of **PT Djakarta Transport Jaya** to increase its sales volume.

- Social media marketing has a positive effect on brand awareness
- Social media marketing has a positive effect on purchase intention

- Competitive pricing has a positive effect on purchase intention
- Quality of service has a positive effect on purchase intention
- Brand awareness positively affects purchase intention

Based on the results of the study, several marketing strategies that can be carried out by PT Djakarta Transport Jaya in increasing brand awareness and increasing sales such as the use of social media platforms can be an effective means to expand reach and accelerate the delivery of production products to remote areas. Then through social media marketing, companies can introduce products or services more effectively, reach target audiences at lower costs, interact directly with consumers, increase customer popularity and trust in the brand, and provide accurate and up-to-date information about the products or services offered. Focusing on service quality and vehicle performance: Good service quality and customer experience can help increase brand awareness and customer trust, thereby increasing satisfaction and attracting more customers.

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